

PROBONO

D5.3 GBN-DT Connectors, Common Data Space and Open Knowledge Base (I)

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DEFINITIONS¹

A Green Building (GB) (new or retrofit) is a building that, in its design, construction and operation, reduces or eliminates negative impacts, and can create positive impacts, on the climate, social, and natural environment. GBs preserve precious natural resources and improve quality of life². Specifically, this means that GBs should be very energy efficient, use extensively the potential of locally available renewable energy, use sustainable materials, and aim for a low environmental impact over the entire life cycle. GBs offer their users and residents a healthy climate and a high quality of stay, they are resilient e.g., to environmental change and contribute to social inclusion.

¹ Please refer to the last submitted reports for the latest status of the definitions

² <https://www.worldgbc.org/what-green-building>

Green Neighbourhoods aligned with the European Green Deal³, is a set of buildings over a delimited area, at a scale that is smaller than a district, with potential synergies, in particular in the area of energy. A green neighbourhood is a neighbourhood that allows for environmentally friendly, sustainable patterns and behaviours to flourish e.g., bioclimatic architecture, renewable energy, soft and zero-emission mobility etc. Green neighbourhoods are the building blocks of Positive Energy Districts (PEDs)⁴ by implementing key elements of PED energy systems. For example, the exchange of energy between buildings increases the share of local self-supply with climate-neutral energy and system efficiency. They also provide the technical conditions to enable Citizen Energy Communities⁵ and Renewable Energy Communities⁶ to be implemented.

Green Buildings and Neighbourhoods (GBN) in PROBONO are GBs integrated at delimited area or district level with green energy and green mobility management and appropriate infrastructure supported by policies, investments and stakeholders' engagement and behaviours that ensures just transition that maximise the economic and social cobenefits considering a district profile (population size, socio-economic structure, and geographical and climate characteristics). Delivered in the right way, GBN infrastructure is a key enabler of inclusive growth, can improve the accessibility of housing and amenities, reduce poverty and inequality, widen access to jobs and education, make communities more resilient to climate change, and promote public health and wellbeing.

DGNB certification serves as a quality stamp ensuring the state of the building for buyers. The Green Building Council Denmark (2010) established the German certification DGNB meaning 'German Society for Sustainable Buildings'. The Danish version of DGNB was created to obtain a common definition of what sustainability is towards and making it measurable. A consortium of experts was established from all parts of the construction sector. DGNB had to be reshaped for the Danish standards, practice, traditions, and laws but is now available to certify any construction project. They chose DGNB as an innovation-forward and sustainable future guarantee. DGNB diversifies itself by focusing on sustainability and not just the environment. DGNB creates a standardised framework for the construction operations conditions and creates a common language which facilitates communication between professions and helps organize and prioritize the efforts in long and complicated development phases.

Life cycle assessment (LCA)⁷ is a tool used for the systematic quantitative assessment of each material used, energy flows and environmental impacts of products or processes. LCA assesses various aspects associated with development of a product and its potential impact throughout a product's life (i.e., cradle to grave) from raw material acquisition, processing, manufacturing, use and finally its disposal. In PROBONO, LCA represents the statement of a building's total energy, resource consumption and environmental impact in the manufacture, transport, and replacement of materials and for its operation over its expected life. Social life cycle assessment (S-LCA)⁸ is a method to assess the social and sociological aspects of products, their actual and potential positive as well as negative impacts along the life cycle. Life-cycle costing (LCC)⁹ considers all the costs incurred during the lifetime of the product, work, or service.

³ European_Green_Deal_EN_200710_fin

⁴ SET-Plan Action 3.2: https://setis.ec.europa.eu/system/files/setplan_smartcities_implementationplan.pdf

⁵ Internal Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944 5 Renewable Energy Directive (EU)

⁶ Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/20012018/2001

⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/16cd2d1d-2216-11e8-ac73-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁸ <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/starting-life-cycle-thinking/life-cycle-approaches/social-lca/>

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/lcc.htm>

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AEC	Architecture Engineering and Construction
AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
API	Application Programming Interface
BAS	Building Automation System
BEMS	Building Energy Management Systems
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BIPV	Building Integrated PhotoVoltaic
BOT	Building Ontology Topology
CDE	Common Data Environment
CSV	Comma Separated Values
CMS	Content Management Systems
DDIM	Dynamic District Infrastructure Management
DHCN	District Heating and Cooling Network
DL	Digital Logbook
ETL	Extract, Transform, and Load
DABGEO	Domain Analysis-Based Global Energy Ontology
DT	Digital Twin
DNAs	Drivers, Needs, Actions and systems
EC	Energy Community
EMS	Energy Management System
ESG	Environmental, Social and Governance
ETL	Extract, Transform, and Load
EV	Electric Vehicle

Acronym	Description
GA	Grant Agreement
GBMS	Green Building Maintenance System
GBN	Green Building Neighbourhood
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IDS	International Data Spaces
IMC	Intelligent Monitoring Control
IoT	Internet of Things
iPaaS	Integration Platform as a Service
IFC	Industry Foundation Class
LL	Living Lab
MDC	Madrid Destruction/Construction
NFT	Non Fungible Token
OKB	Open Knowledge Base
OWL	Ontology Web Language
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RES	Renewable Energy Source
SAREF	Smart Appliances Reference
SHIP	Solar Heat for Industrial Processes
SNS	Simple Notification Service
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier

1 Executive summary

The goal of T5.2 is primarily linked with the WP5 objectives (b) “design and implement the infrastructure supporting the GBN-DP” and (c) “define and construct information and simulation models while ensuring their interoperability & integration”. The task expected outcomes are threefold and include i) the development of data connectors to support integration of heterogeneous data sources embedding monitoring, visualization and automation ii) the building of a common data space, leveraging state-of-the-art linked data technologies to expose all gathered data in a semantically rich, uniform manner, facilitating as such the interconnection of heterogeneous, data-centric, subsystems iii) the creation of an open Knowledge Base acting as a single point of reference to share knowledge and information with respect to the GBN domain and the application of the PROBONO technologies in the project LLs.

D5.3 is the first of a series of three deliverables reporting the work conducted under T5.2 and, as such, it contains the outcomes from the design phase of the technical components developed in this task, including the studying of project LL requirements and the investigation of state-of-the-art technologies and tools that are relevant to the project goals. In particular, the high-level architecture of the Intelligent Monitoring and Control (IMC) connectors and the common data space components is detailed in this deliverable, as well as the initial structure of the open Knowledge Base and the tools that it will employ. Finally, with regard to T5.3 “GBN-DT Global Decision Support and Optimization Platform”, an initial set of requirements in terms of data endpoints needed by the GBN-DT platform is included as well.

2 Introduction

We begin by positioning the deliverable content vis-a-vis the task specifications, as indicated in the project GA, to provide to the reader a quick view of how this work delivers the prescribed goals. Subsequently, we briefly indicate the purpose and scope of this document, as well as its relation with other project tasks, and finally the rationale for the way it has been structured.

2.1 Mapping PROBONO outputs

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASK			
T5.2 GBN-DT Connectors, Common Data Space and Open Knowledge Base	ST5.2.1 Intelligent GBN subsystems Monitoring Control (IMC) Connectors. Define, design, and deploy the infrastructure to connect the GBN platform external systems data sources, including sensors, external databases.	Chapter 3, sections 3.1-2	The process of requirement analysis and system design for the IMC connectors is described in these sections.

	<p>A central IMC Connectors module will (a) Manage device authentication, end-to-end encryption (b) Streaming and Queuing message exchanges (Apache Kafka, Apache Pulsar) (c) Automate deployment (Kubernetes) and cluster configurations for increased message loads and efficiency in processing, (d) Embed monitoring and visualisation via a Management and configuration UI (e.g. Grafana), (e) Integrate CHARIoT blockchain-based PKI for sensor and gateway authentication and blockchain aided encryption of IoT endpoints, (f) Cover Smart contracts for process automation (certification process, contract process), secure IOT, DT Data transparency and trust. The connectors will enable connection with other data exchange platforms (such as e-delivery, X-Road, etc.). All APIs developed and deployed in the context of a PROBONO Living Lab will become available via an API Registry that will notably include automated technical documentation and implementation synchronisation</p>	<p>Chapter 3, section 3.3</p>	<p>The specific components aimed to deliver the functionalities described are detailed as part of the IMC connector architecture.</p>
	<p>ST5.2.2 Common GBN Data Space, Semantics and Linked Data Infrastructure. Provide the semantic broker which combines data coming from various IMC Connectors as a 'data lake' used by the simulation and optimisation modules of the GBN-DT. The DDIM server will be used to integrate various data sources expressed as Linked Data. The DDIM architecture will describe a common structure onto which data in various formats can be mapped to create a single overarching linked data space, building on outputs from T3.1 and T4.1. A data-register will facilitate data discovery by GBN-DT clients. The data sources can be imported and managed by the server or hosted remotely and accessed using federated (remote) queries. Different data formats are supported, including</p>	<p>Chapter 4</p>	<p>This document chapter delves into the DDIM server and the way it is positioned in the Common GBN Data Space, as well as the manner it interacts with the IMC connectors.</p>

	<p>custom integrations with IFC and CityGML. The server will provide a query interface that supports SPARQL queries to Linked-Data sources.</p>		
	<p>ST5.2.3 GBN Open Knowledge Base. Innovations Observatory for enhanced visibility on the performance of GBN solutions across the sector, incorporating from WP1-WP4 and knowledge gained from LLs. The task will use a structured methodology to build on the results of the most relevant projects to date, in the domain of digitized GBNs. This Knowledge Base (improved with the analysis of use cases and concrete problems faced by the LLs) will serve as a reference on practices and solutions responding to interoperability, the applicable legal frameworks, privacy, licensing, data governance mechanisms in place, standards, and technological challenges. The Open KB will notably: (a) Identify relevant data sources across the GBN technologies (b) Capture relevant LL for decision support (c) Classify data by frequency, pertinence, scope, users, providers, etc. (d) Engage GBN Data Hub users and perform evaluation.</p>	<p>Chapter 5</p>	<p>This chapter describes the methodology followed to design the GBN Open Knowledge Base, according to the specifications indicated in the task description.</p>
DELIVERABLE			
<p>D5.3 GBN-DT Connectors, Common Data Space and Knowledge Base (I) This report formulates the findings of T5.2, and explores step/s A) Initial build of GBN-DT data components.</p>			

Table 1. Task outputs mapped to GA description

2.2 Purpose and scope of the document

T5.2, "GBN-DT Connectors, Common Data Space, and Open Knowledge Base," is broken down in three subtasks, with the overarching goal of providing the necessary infrastructure supporting connectivity, data management, and knowledge sharing within the GBN-DT platform. The first subtask (ST5.2.1) focuses on the development of the Intelligent GBN subsystems Monitoring Control (IMC) connectors, which will enable the connection of diverse data sources to the GBN

platform; ST5.2.2 corresponds to the building of a common GBN data space, leveraging linked data infrastructure and ST5.2.3 involves the building of an Open Knowledge Base, capturing all information and insights from the PROBONO outcomes and their application in the project Living Labs (LL).

The task work is partitioned in three distinct phases, namely the design phase, the testing phase and the operational phase, as depicted in *Figure 1* below.

Figure 1. T5.2 high level work plan

As this is the first of a series of three deliverables of T5.2 with delivery date at M18, its purpose is to report the outcomes of the work conducted during the design phase of the task. This crucial stage follows the gathering of requirements and entails the creation of detailed plans and specifications to guide the development and implementation of the T5.2 technical components. The design phase encompasses activities such as architectural design, system analysis and interface design. It involves collaborative efforts from technical teams across various project WPs to determine the desired structure, behaviour, and functionality of the GBN connectors, common data space and Open KB. Emphasizing technical challenges, scalability, maintainability, and reliability, this phase facilitates informed decision-making regarding technology choices and implementation strategies.

2.3 Structure of the document and its relationship with other WPS/Deliverables

This deliverable is structured in three core chapters (Chapter 3, 4, and 5), corresponding to each of the T5.1 subtasks, followed by a brief conclusion (Chapter 6). More specifically, Chapter 3 presents the IMC components mapping it to PROBONO LL data requirements, Chapter 4 details

the work undertaken for the design of the GBN-DT common data space, and Chapter 5 includes the specifications of the open KB.

Relation with other Work Packages/Deliverables

The identified links between this deliverable and other work packages /deliverables are outlined below:

WP3 - PROBONO Smart Green Building Construction and Renovation

- WP3 will provide digital models that will be integrated in the PROBONO-DT, therefore the data endpoints in the GBN common data space will have to provide a compliant format (or vice versa) so the data can be consumed properly. D3.1 - "SOTA Reports and DT Models (I)" and D5.1 – "GBN-DT Requirements and Specifications (I)" contain a high-level description of the models although more precise requirements will have to be defined to ensure seamless integration.

WP4 - Energy Monitoring and Clean Energy Production, Storage and Distribution

- WP4 will deliver technological tools that will interact directly or indirectly with the PROBONO DT. T5.2 will support this integration via the IMC Connectors and the overarching linked data space.

WP5 - Digitalisation for data driven GBN human-centred design and construction/renovation and operations optimisation

- T5.2 heavily relies in the requirements gathering happening in T5.1 and reported under D5.1 and D5.2, aiming to deliver technical solutions which fulfil, as much as possible, those specifications. Moreover, T5.2 is directly linked with the work taking place in T5.3 concerning the GBN platform, which will host the models and systems that will consume the data gathered using the infrastructure provided by T5.2.

WP6 - Monitoring and evaluation of the project's Living Labs

- T5.2 may need to incorporate specific data schemas to support the KPIs defined under WP6 and their calculation. Generic requirements have been outlined in D6.1, however more detailed specifications of each KPIs to be implemented are needed and will be given by WP6 in the future.

WP7 - Living Labs GBN Implementation

- The WP5 components are going to be demonstrated in project LLs hence the work undergone in WP7 is also linked with T5.2, as the LL planning and implementation schedule affect the corresponding testing and integration activities.

In addition to the above and as described in the GA, the Open Knowledge Base (OKB) will serve as an innovations observatory, combining open data sources with evaluation data from all the LLs, offering access to GBN models produced by WP1-4.

2.4 Contribution to GBN concept

In the realm of GBNs, harnessing the power of data and technology is becoming increasingly important. Data connectors play a crucial role in facilitating seamless integration and interoperability within GBNs, and to that end the IMC connectors, developed in T5.2, aim to support the seamless exchange of information and real-time data between various components within the neighborhood ecosystem. The IMC connectors are designed to ensure a smooth flow of data between smart buildings, energy management systems and other key infrastructure of the GBNs. This interconnectedness allows for efficient monitoring, control, and optimization of resources, leading to enhanced energy efficiency and sustainability within GBNs.

To fully capitalize on the potential of data generated by different systems within GBNs, T5.2 will leverage linked data technology. The GBN common data space will act as a central repository for storing and organizing diverse datasets related to energy consumption and other relevant metrics, establishing semantic connections between which will allow for holistic insights and analysis. This comprehensive understanding of data empowers stakeholders, including residents, planners, and policymakers, to make informed decisions and devise effective strategies for sustainable development and resource optimization.

Finally, an open Knowledge Base serves as a valuable resource within Green Building Neighborhoods, fostering collaboration, innovation, and knowledge sharing. The PROBONO Open KB is designed to consolidate best practices, case studies, research findings, and technological advancements in sustainable urban development, acting as a collective knowledge management tool across the whole project. It will act as a hub for residents, developers, and researchers to access and contribute to a wealth of information. By leveraging this collective knowledge, GBN stakeholders can implement innovative solutions, replicate successful models, and continuously improve the sustainability and livability of their neighborhoods.

3 Intelligent Monitoring Control Connectors

The IMC data connectors serve as the bridge between the physical world and the digital representation of assets in the PROBONO digital twin environment. They act as a middleware layer, responsible for collecting, transforming, and transmitting data from various sources to the digital twin platform. By providing support for both streaming data and static datasets, the IMC connectors support the DT modelers in creating comprehensive and accurate digital replicas that reflect the real-time state of the corresponding physical entities.

In this chapter, the results from the design phase of the IMC connectors are presented in detail. First, a brief description of the background and the state-of-the-art investigated in the field is included. Then the IMC connectors derived functional architecture is presented, depicting the envisioned technical components, followed by a technical overview of each component in terms of specific features and implementation technologies.

3.1 Background on Data Connectors

3.1.1 State of the art solutions

Data connectors are software tools that enable different applications, databases, and systems to exchange data with each other seamlessly. The primary objective of a data connector is to enable data to flow between different systems without manual intervention, reducing the chances of errors and delays caused by manual data entry.

The state of the art in the field of data connectors is constantly evolving, and there are various approaches to building and implementing them. Some of the most commonly used methods for developing data connectors include [1]:

- **Application Programming Interfaces (APIs):** APIs are the most widely used method of building data connectors. APIs provide a standard interface for different applications to exchange data with each other.
- **Middleware:** Middleware is software that acts as a bridge between different systems, enabling data exchange between them. Middleware solutions include Enterprise Service Bus (ESB) and message queues.

- **Extract, Transform, and Load (ETL) tools:** ETL tools are used to extract data from different sources, transform it to meet the requirements of the target system, and load it into the target system.
- **Data virtualization:** Data virtualization tools enable data to be accessed from different sources without replicating it, thus reducing data redundancy.
- **Integration Platform as a Service (iPaaS):** iPaaS is a cloud-based platform that provides pre-built connectors to enable data integration between different systems.

In recent years, there has been a growing trend towards building data connectors using low-code or no-code platforms, which enable non-technical users to build connectors quickly and easily. Overall, the state of the art in the field of data connectors is constantly evolving, with new technologies and approaches being developed to simplify data integration between different systems [2].

3.1.2 Enabling Technologies

In the building sector, there exist several technologies that are often leveraged to build data connectors to support automation and energy management systems. In this section, we summarize the most prominent ones, which were evaluated at the design phase of the IMC connectors for use in PROBONO. Besides looking at a single level, we focus also on the district level, to be able to accommodate data exchange and interoperability between various buildings, systems, and stakeholders, leading to enhanced energy efficiency, sustainability, and optimization for GBNs.

Internet of Things (IoT) Platforms: IoT platforms have revolutionized the building sector by connecting devices and sensors to enable smarter and more efficient operations. These platforms facilitate real-time monitoring and control of various building systems, such as HVAC, lighting, security, and energy management. By integrating data from temperature sensors, occupancy detectors, and other sources, IoT platforms provide valuable insights into energy consumption, occupant comfort, and equipment performance. For instance, an IoT platform can collect data from temperature and occupancy sensors in a building, analyze it, and adjust the HVAC system accordingly to optimize energy usage and occupant comfort. Furthermore, at the district level, IoT platforms can aggregate data from multiple buildings to optimize district-wide energy consumption, balance energy supply and demand, and enable efficient resource management.

Building Automation Systems (BAS): Building Automation Systems are comprehensive solutions that centralize the control and monitoring of a building's critical functions. BAS leverage data connectors to enable seamless communication and information exchange between different subsystems, such as HVAC, lighting, access control, and security. This integration allows for centralized monitoring, efficient energy management, and automated responses to changing conditions, also applicable at the district level. For example, a data connector can integrate the fire alarm system with the HVAC system, triggering automatic ventilation shutdown and fire damper activation, as well as notifying the adjacent buildings, in case of a fire emergency.

Building Energy Management Systems (BEMS): Building Energy Management Systems focus on optimizing energy consumption, reducing waste, and improving overall energy efficiency in buildings. Data connectors within BEMS enable the integration of data from diverse sources, such as smart meters, weather forecasts, occupancy sensors, and utility providers. By leveraging this integrated data, BEMS can perform advanced energy analytics, demand response management, and implement energy-saving strategies. While BAS focuses on overall building automation and control, including energy-related systems, BEMS specifically targets energy management and optimization. BEMS can be considered as a subset or specialized component within a BAS, with a particular emphasis on energy-related data integration, analytics, and energy efficiency strategies. The integration of both systems can result in comprehensive building management solutions that combine automation, control, and energy optimization capabilities. Moreover, a district BEMS can aggregate data from multiple buildings to identify energy-saving opportunities, implement demand response strategies across the district, and optimize the overall energy consumption and cost also at the district level.

Cloud-based Data Platforms: Cloud-based data platforms offer scalable and centralized storage, processing, and analysis capabilities for building-related data. These platforms serve as a repository for data collected from various sources, such as sensors, building management systems, possibly from multiple buildings, as well as external data providers. By integrating and analyzing this data, cloud-based platforms enable building owners or district energy managers to gain valuable insights, identify trends, and make data-driven decisions. Facility managers can leverage these platforms to monitor energy consumption, optimize maintenance schedules, and improve overall building performance. Additionally, cloud-based platforms support remote access, collaboration, and provide a foundation for implementing machine learning algorithms and predictive analytics.

In the following table, we summarize the main advantages and disadvantages of the above-mentioned technologies, with the goal of identifying the best fitting ones for the purpose of the project.

Technology	Advantages	Disadvantages
IoT Platforms	Real-time monitoring and control	Security and privacy concerns
	Integration of diverse devices and sensors	Reliance on stable network connectivity
	Enhanced energy efficiency and occupant comfort	Potential scalability challenges in handling data from multiple buildings within a district
Building Automation Systems	Centralized control and monitoring	Initial setup and installation costs
	Efficient response to changing conditions	Potential compatibility issues between different subsystems
	Improved energy management and automation	Dependency on reliable power supply
	Enhanced security and safety	Need for regular system maintenance and updates
Building Energy Management Systems	Optimized energy consumption and cost savings	Initial investment in hardware, sensors, and data connectors
	Integration of diverse data sources for advanced analytics	Complexity in integrating data from various systems and sensors
	Demand response capabilities and energy-saving strategies applicable also at a district level	Dependence on accurate data collection and calibration
	Improved sustainability and environmental impact	Data privacy concerns and compliance with regulations
Cloud-based Data Platforms	Scalable storage and processing capabilities	Potential security vulnerabilities if not properly secured
	Centralized data management and accessibility	Reliance on internet connectivity for remote access and collaboration

	Advanced analytics and insights	Ongoing subscription or usage fees for cloud services
	Enables machine learning and predictive analytics	Data transfer and latency issues in large-scale deployments

Table 2: Pros and cons of different connector technologies in the building sector

We note here that while these pros and cons provide a good insight, the specific advantages and disadvantages may vary depending on the implementation, configuration, and specific use cases. Under this light, the ultimate choice of technologies would depend highly on the project LL requirements, discussed in the following section.

3.2 Data Connector Requirements in PROBONO

This section presents the identified data connector requirements for the PROBONO Digital Twin, based on the requirements gathered so far in T5.1 - “GBN DT Requirements Specification and Architecture” which are reported in D5.1. In particular, the data inventories listed in D5.1 were analyzed by data source, and in each case the corresponding connector requirements were identified. This process was effectuated in collaboration with the corresponding LL technical personnel, to ensure the correctness of the derived technical requirements. The results are presented below in concentrated tables per project Living Lab. Regarding data not yet available for inspection at the LLs, the necessary information for the connectors was conveyed during dedicated technical calls.

3.2.1 Dublin LL

The Living Lab of Dublin considers data sources coming from 3 buildings, its occupants, and a surrounding EV grid ecosystem. Table 3 below presents a concentrated view on the gathered connector requirements:

Data source	Content description	Availability	Connector Requirements
Electric Energy Meter	Monthly meter reading	yes	Excel sheets available, ingested via custom API calls encapsulating appropriate data parsing.
Gas Meter	Monthly meter reading	yes	
Woodchip Meter	Monthly reading, woodchip weight	Yes	

Gas and Energy Pricing	Monthly bills	yes	
HVAC	Sensor readings	No, when sensors are installed	API calls either from the LL side or the DT platform, to be defined.
BMS	Temperature, set point, energy consumption	Not yet	
Ambient Sensors	CO2, Humidity, Temperature Occupancy	Not yet	
EV charging station	Current charging station status	no	
EV vehicle	Vehicle data including location, current user and charge status and charge levels	no	
Weather data on precise location and forecast	Sun radiation (sun position in time), clouds, temperature humidity, wind, precipitation	yes	Ingest via publicly available APIs and match with rest of LL data.
Air quality	Google air quality Sensor attached at the outside of the building at various levels (height)	yes	
Noise level	Sensor readings around and inside of the building at various locations	No, when sensors are installed	REST API calls either from the LL side or the DT platform, to be defined.
Lightning level	Sensor readings inside building	No, when sensors are installed	
Windows state	Sensor readings inside building	No, when sensors are installed	
Waste management report	Report on waste production	No, when procedure or sensors are established	
Car park state	Current charge status and levels and parking location for each vehicle in the fleet	No, when sensors are installed	
Charging station network	Location and state of our charging network	no	Static data ingested once either manually or via API call. State of network updated periodically via API call either from LL system or DT platform, to be defined.
Weekly meal reports	Canteen delivers report on meal preparation and consumption also a report on waste produced	no	Automatic text extraction from handwritten reports, or exposure of web form for manual data ingestion.
Person locations	Staff use their card for presence and time tracking	yes (partially)	REST API calls either from the LL side or the DT platform, to be defined.

Presence detection	Staff is usually assigned to particular office or location, where presence/counter sensors are to be installed. Citizens are also included and they are localized to public service area.	no	
Incident reports	Incidents that are reported by staff	no	
Elevator reading	There are more than one elevator and current elevator state should be visible	no	
Interior setup report	Map of interior elements like plants and air purifiers.	no	

Table 3: Dublin LL data connector requirements

3.2.2 Madrid Geothermal Plant LL

The MGP LL involves data corresponding to the construction of 2 buildings and a District Cooling and Heating Network (DHCN), upon demolition of the previous buildings in the same area. The following table presents the data connector requirements:

Data source	Content description	Availability	Connector Requirements
BIM Models	a) one for the two buildings to be developed b) another for the geothermal plant from IDOM and including among other things DHCN structure and design.	a) DHCN BIM already available b) Building BIM not available at this moment	Infrastructural data from the DHCN BIM will be ingested once via a REST API call. As more data/metadata become available in the BIMs, their ingestion method will be defined.
User patterns	Information about user patterns based on thermal setpoint changes, occupancy provided by a monitoring system.	Not available yet (buildings not selected nor constructed)	REST API calls either from the LL side or the DT platform, to be defined.
Weather forecast data	External weather forecast service	Not defined yet	
DHCN Monitored Data - Ground loop system	The data concerns the Ground loop system based on 60-80 boreholes (For each of the loops), for example, the electricity consumption of the pumps, the flow rate, the energy exchanged, etc.	Not available yet (available once DHCN will be constructed and deployed)	REST API calls either from the LL side or the DT platform, to be defined when the DHCN will be completed.
DHCN Monitored Data - Heat Pump system / Geothermal plant	The data concerns the Heat Pump system/Geothermal plant (For each of the Heat pumps), for example: Electricity	Not available yet (available once DHCN will be	

	consumption/Pumps, Evaporator side: Flow, Evaporator side: Temperature supply / return, Condenser side: Flow, Condenser side: Temperature supply / return, Condenser side: Energy...	constructed and deployed)	
DHCN Monitored Data - Heating and cooling distribution network (Pipes).	The dataset concerns the Heating and cooling distribution network (Pipes) including variables such as: Pumps electricity consumption, Flow, Temperatures supply/return, Energy Provided.	Not available yet (available once DHCN will be constructed and deployed)	

Table 4: MGP LL data connector requirements

3.2.3 Madrid Destruction/Construction LL

The MDC LL includes data corresponding to a recycling plant for construction and demolition materials, operating in the pilot site.

Data source	Content description	Availability	Connector Requirements
BIM Models	BIM model of the buildings and infrastructure projects of the district that will be built, with schedule information, and bill of materials	yes	BIM models can contain a multitude of datasets so each case will have to be investigated individually. Depending on the case, custom parsers will be implemented on the connector side.
Existing buildings and infrastructure	Information about existing buildings and infrastructure to be demolished, including materials compositions.	yes	Static data ingested once either manually or via REST API call.
Timeline of recycling process	Information about the process of recycling process, with a timeline of activities since the entry point of demolition waste until the output of recycled materials and products.	no	
Timeline of projects	Schedule of the construction of new buildings and infrastructure, to plan the assignment of resources and the storage of materials at the recycling plant.	yes	
Space allocation	Specific plot of the recycling plant with building information regarding storage capacity of recycled materials.	no	REST API calls with periodic scheduling either from the LL side or the DT platform, to be defined.
Percentage of salvaged materials	Relation of recycled materials coming out of the process with the input amount from the demolition	no	

Air quality	Satellite-derived air pollutants and aerosols	no	
Meteorological data	Environmental data	no	
Lidar	Time series characterizing atmospheric aerosols	no	

Table 5: MDC LL data connector requirements

3.2.4 Porto LL

Data from the internal data systems at Porto LL will be gathered via a dedicated gateway server, deployed specifically for the project purposes. This gateway will be linked with the relevant systems that are already in place (BMS, Weather stations, RES production units, EV grid) and from there the data will be forwarded to the PROBONO DT via REST API calls. Furthermore, the additional innovations delivered during the PROBONO project (BIPV, SHIP, V2G, Smart EV Hub, PCM) will either connect to this gateway as well or directly communicate with the DT platform. In the following table, the data connector requirements for Porto LL are presented in a concentrated manner:

Data Source	Content description	Availability	Connector Requirements
BMS	Electricity consumption	No	Data ingested in gateway server connected with the DT Platform via REST APIs
PV Plant	Electricity production	No	
EV Hub	Electric vehicle data	No	
Weather station	Incident solar radiation in the PV, ambient temperature	No	
Innovations Data - BIPV	Energy Projection	No	Connection with dedicated gateway or directly with the DT platform via REST APIs
Innovations Data - SHIP	SHIP (Solar Heat for Industrial Processes) technology to implement in the Campus	No	
Innovations Data - V2G	Power of the V2G solution to implement at the Campus	No	
Innovations Data - Smart EV Hub	Electricity consumption of the EV HUB chargers, occupancy patterns and more	No	
Innovations Data - PCM at warehouse	Electricity consumption of the cooling system	No	

Table 6: Porto LL data connector requirements

3.2.5 Brussels LL

In the Living Lab of Brussels, the data to be ingested originate from a school building and include energy monitoring data, as well as data related to user mobility in the LL area.

Data Source	Content description	Availability	Connector Requirements
3D models	Architectural and CAD drawings of the school	Yes	Static data ingested once via REST API call with custom parser.
Historical energy data	Energy demand, consumption, production, pricing	Partially	
IoT sensor and actuator data	Humidity, luminosity, CO2, pressure, voltage, door and window states	Not yet	This data will be gathered in a gateway platform deployed on site (developed under T4.2 “GBN Demand and Response Platform”) and the DT will connect with this platform via REST APIs to set up data ingestion schemes.
Weather data	Open data	Yes	Ingest via publicly available APIs and match with rest of LL data.
Brussels mobility data	Open data related to mobility in the Brussels-Capital region, including pedestrian mobility patterns, traffic flows and more.	Yes	

Table 7: Brussels LL data connector requirements

3.2.6 Aarhus LL

The Aarhus LL requires data connectors for ingesting energy-related data related to 2 buildings, as well as certain occupant preferences as detailed in the table below:

Data Source	Content description	Availability	Connector Requirements
3D model of buildings (BIM models)	Both building projects (the Kitchen 2.0 and BSS, consisting of 3-4 buildings)	Yes	The BIM models will be investigated individually and depending on the data consumer requirements (energy models etc) appropriate parsers will be implemented on the connector side.
Energy data	Data from sensors and meters in the buildings (electricity, heating, room temperature and water consumption)	No	REST API calls either from the LL side or the DT platform, to be defined.
LCA metrics and human-centred criteria	DGNB indicator scores, Air quality, Thermal comfort	Not yet	Static data ingested once via REST API.
Human-centred criteria	Thermal comfort	Not yet	

Table 8: Aarhus LL data connector requirements

3.2.7 Prague LL

The Living Lab of Prague involves data sources coming from 4 buildings, with a focus on energy as well as occupancy.

Data Source	Content description	Availability	Connector Requirements
Electricity Meters	Electricity consumption at all LL buildings	Not yet	REST API calls either from the LL side or the DT platform, to be defined.
Heat Meters	Heat consumption at all LL buildings	Not yet	
IoT ambient sensors	Temperature, Humidity, CO2, VOC at each room of building B	Not yet	
Energy consumption data	Energy consumption for lightning, cooling and other systems at building B	Not yet	
Weather data	Weather station installed on-site	Not yet	
Occupancy information	Number of people in the building A, B, C and D	Not yet	
Open data	Various datasets collected and made public by city council	Yes	Static data ingested once via REST API, filtering necessary.

Table 9: Prague LL data connector requirements

3.3 The IMC Connector Architecture

With the above requirements in mind and considering the state-of-the-art data connector solutions, the IMC architecture was defined. The goal was to achieve robustness and scalability to support continuous influx of information and ensure efficient data processing. The architecture of the IMC connector comprises several key elements, as illustrated in *Figure 2*, each serving a specific purpose in the data integration process.

Figure 2. IMC Connector high level architecture

At the forefront, there is a **data ingestion module** responsible for capturing data from diverse sources, including IoT sensors, gateways, and external systems. This module will be designed to handle data in various formats and protocols, ensuring compatibility and flexibility to accommodate the different data sources. As such, it is depicted having different instances in the architectural schema (IMC1, IMC2 and so on) reflecting the specific needs of each of the data sources. Each IMC instance also encapsulates data transformation and normalization layer, as well appropriate authentication and encryption processes. This layer is responsible for harmonizing the incoming data, converting it into a standardized format suitable for further processing and analysis. It applies necessary data cleansing techniques, resolves inconsistencies, and enriches the information when required. It acts as a data refinery, ensuring that the digital twin receives accurate and reliable data for modeling and simulation. Following the data transformation stage, the architecture incorporates a **message broker** which handles incoming data offering publish/subscribe functionalities, to deliver streaming data to interested consumers or simply direct data to a data storage component.

In addition to the core data integration and processing components, the connector architecture includes a **management and configuration** component. This component provides a user-friendly interface for administrators and developers to configure and manage the data connector's settings, monitor the health and performance of the system, and visualize the data being ingested and processed. This empowers users to monitor the status of data sources, track data flow, set up data mappings and transformations, define access controls, and configure integration with external systems, enhancing the overall usability and control of the data connector.

Finally, a cutting-edge addition to the data connector architecture is the integration of a **digital logbook** utilizing blockchain technology. The digital logbook built on a blockchain provides an immutable and transparent ledger that records selected data or metrics ingested from the specific LL. By leveraging the decentralized and tamper-resistant nature of blockchain, the digital logbook ensures the integrity and traceability of data transactions, enhancing the trustworthiness and auditability of the digital twin environment. This integration fosters accountability and enhances data governance, making it an invaluable component for compliance-driven industries or scenarios where regulatory requirements demand a high level of data integrity and transparency.

All data transactions in the IMC connector will be fulfilled via RESTful APIs, the details of which will be consolidated in a dedicated **API registry** including technical documentation. In the rest of this section, we go over the authentication measures, before detailing the specificities of the key components as well as the envisioned implementation technologies.

3.3.1 Authentication

Authentication plays a crucial role in ensuring secure access and usage of the data handled by the IMC connectors within the PROBONO project. Various authentication solutions and enabling technologies will be considered, depending on the specific requirements, to establish robust authentication mechanisms. The key solutions that will be considered are the following:

- **Username/Password Authentication:** This traditional approach involves users providing a unique username and a corresponding password to authenticate their identity. The data connectors verify the provided credentials against stored records to grant access. While widely used, it's important to ensure strong password policies, such as complexity requirements and regular password updates, to enhance security.

- **Token-Based Authentication:** Token-based authentication has gained popularity due to its flexibility and improved security. It involves generating a unique token after successful authentication, which is then used for subsequent requests. Tokens can be short-lived and can be refreshed periodically, enhancing security by minimizing the need to transmit passwords with every request.
- **Single Sign-On (SSO):** SSO solutions enable users to authenticate once and gain access to multiple systems or services without requiring separate credentials for each. This streamlines the authentication process and improves user experience. Common SSO protocols include OAuth and SAML, which allow secure authentication and authorization across multiple domains or systems.
- **Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA):** MFA adds an extra layer of security by combining two or more authentication factors, such as something the user knows (password), something the user has (smart card), or something the user is (biometric data). Implementing MFA provides an additional safeguard against unauthorized access, even if one factor is compromised.

A combination of existing technological enablers, such as **JSON Web Tokens (JWT)**, **OpenID Connect (OIDC)**, **Lightweight Directory Access Protocol (LDAP)**, and **Security Assertion Markup Language (SAML)**, will be utilized to implement the above processes in the IMC connectors. Careful consideration of security requirements, user needs, and overall system architecture will play an important role in selecting the most appropriate methods in each case.

3.3.2 Message Broker

The message broker acts as a robust intermediary between the data sources and the rest of the connector components, facilitating the seamless flow of data and enabling efficient communication and integration. It serves as a central hub where data is collected, transformed, and dispatched in a scalable and decoupled manner, while ensuring reliable delivery by handling potential network disruptions or system failures through features like message persistence and delivery acknowledgment.

One of the key advantages of utilizing a message broker is its ability to decouple data producers from consumers. This decoupling allows data sources to operate independently, sending data to the message broker without having direct knowledge of the recipients, in an event-driven architecture (*Figure 3*). Consumers, on the other hand, can subscribe to specific data streams or topics of interest, enabling a publish-subscribe pattern. This architecture fosters flexibility,

scalability, and modularity, as new data sources or consumers can be added or removed without disrupting the overall system. Through its decoupling capabilities, the message broker enables data producers to operate independently, enabling real-time data streaming and facilitating the integration of various components within the whole digital twin platform. For example, the message broker can direct incoming data to a data lake for storage and analysis, while feeding selected data to the digital logbook and simultaneously direct data streams to subscribed DT applications.

Figure 3 Event-driven architecture

There exist several implementation technologies for message brokers that can be utilized in the architecture of the data connector. One widely adopted technology is **Apache Kafka**, an open-source distributed streaming platform. Kafka offers high-throughput, fault-tolerant messaging and provides strong durability guarantees for data storage. Its distributed nature allows for horizontal scalability and fault tolerance, making it suitable for handling large volumes of streaming data. Another popular option is **RabbitMQ**, an open-source message broker that implements the Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP). RabbitMQ is known for its reliability, supporting various messaging patterns such as point-to-point, publish-subscribe, and request-reply. It provides features like message routing, delivery acknowledgments, and support for multiple programming languages, making it a versatile choice for building scalable and resilient data connector architectures.

Additionally, cloud-based message brokers like **Amazon Simple Notification Service (SNS)** and **Google Cloud Pub/Sub** offer managed messaging solutions with extensive scalability and reliability features. These cloud offerings abstract the underlying infrastructure and provide easy integration with other cloud services, making them convenient choices for organizations leveraging cloud platforms. When selecting a message broker factors such as reliability,

performance, security, and ease of integration should be considered. Table 10 presents a comparison of the above technologies on certain key aspects:

Technology	Throughput	Fault Tolerance	Data Storage	Messaging Patterns	Security	Other Features
Apache Kafka	High	Yes	Durable	Publish-Subscribe, Point-to-Point, Request-Reply	SSL/TLS encryption, Authentication	Suitable for handling large volumes of streaming data
RabbitMQ	Limited	Yes	Durable	Publish-Subscribe, Point-to-Point, Request-Reply	SSL/TLS encryption, Authentication, Authorization	Implements the Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP)
Amazon SNS	High	Yes	-	Publish-Subscribe	Encryption in transit, Access control policies	Cloud-based, Abstracts underlying infrastructure
Google Cloud	High	Yes	-	Publish-Subscribe	Encryption in transit and at rest, Identity and access management	Cloud-based, Abstracts underlying infrastructure

Table 10: Comparison of message broker solutions

For the purposes of PROBONO, after careful consideration of the available technologies and the collected LL data requirements, Apache Kafka has been selected as the preferred choice. Apache Kafka stands out as a high-throughput distributed streaming platform, making it an ideal candidate for handling the large volumes of streaming data generated by IoT devices and other data sources in the context of digital building twins. Its fault-tolerant and durable data storage capabilities ensure the reliability and integrity of data, while its horizontal scalability allows for seamless expansion as the digital twin ecosystem grows.

3.3.3 Blockchain-based Digital Logbook

Leveraging the decentralized and immutable nature of blockchain, the Digital Logbook (DL) offers an innovative solution to achieve trustworthy and intelligent decision making in the GBN-DT platform. This brings together building owners, occupants, actors of the Architecture Engineering and Construction (AEC) sector, technology providers, financial institutions, and public authorities enabling transparent reporting in the Green Building Neighbourhood. The proposed integration of the DL, the DT and the Blockchain (*Figure 4*) attempts to combine the best of both worlds; so, it proposes a hybrid blockchain infrastructure for scalability and identity verification of private blockchains as well as trust and decentralisation of public blockchains.

Figure 4. Digital Logbook, Digital Building Twins and Blockchain

The above architecture enables end users to store energy consumption and GHG emissions-related data for buildings on a private Blockchain for confidentiality and security and at the same time to issue NFTs on a public Blockchain to increase accountability and transparency. NFTs can be utilized by NFT owners to prove the achievement of energy KPIS to authorities or other actors of the ecosystem. Furthermore, and in addition to energy performance data, the private blockchain can store buildings' metadata, enabling this way the unified, systematic, well-organised and standardised monitoring of buildings' performance across a wider area, city or region. Meanwhile, smart contract based automation can be used to standardise the process of gathering measurements and reporting them on-chain to be accessed by all the involved stakeholders.

3.3.4 Management and Configuration User Interface

The management and configuration component in the IMC connector provides a user-friendly interface for administrators and developers to configure, monitor, and manage the incoming data flows. At a high level, the management and configuration component allow users to efficiently configure and manage data sources, define data mappings and transformations, set up access controls and monitor the overall health and performance of the system.

In selecting the optimal technology for this component, several implementation technologies were reviewed during the IMC design phase. The most prominent ones include:

- **Kibana:** Kibana, part of the Elastic Stack, is an open-source data visualization and exploration tool. It offers powerful search capabilities, interactive visualizations, and real-time data analytics. With Kibana, users can create custom dashboards and reports to monitor the performance and health of the data connector, as well as analyze streaming and static data.
- **Tableau:** Tableau is a widely used business intelligence and analytics platform that provides intuitive data visualization and reporting capabilities. With Tableau, users can create interactive dashboards and perform ad-hoc analysis, making it an excellent choice for monitoring and managing the data connector's performance and data quality.
- **Grafana** is a powerful open-source analytics and monitoring platform that offers rich visualization capabilities. It allows users to create custom dashboards with various data visualizations, such as graphs, charts, and tables, providing real-time insights into the data connector's performance, data ingestion rates, and system health.

In the context of PROBONO, the solution selected for this component is Grafana coupled also by **Prometheus**, a feature-rich open-source monitoring system specifically designed for time-series data. By leveraging Grafana and Prometheus as the management and configuration components, the IMC connector can benefit from their robust features and capabilities; together, they form a powerful combination that enhances the management, monitoring, and configuration aspects, facilitating effective control and troubleshooting within the digital twin environment. An example dashboard is depicted in *Figure 5* below.

Figure 5. Grafana and Prometheus dashboard example

4 GBN Common Data Space

During the common data space design phase, we initially considered incorporating the International Data Spaces (IDS) framework for data sharing in the GBN architecture. However, after a thorough evaluation, we concluded that the complexity and setup required for implementing IDS components exceeded the requirements of PROBONO. Since our focus was primarily to achieve efficient data management and integration within the GBN ecosystem, we determined that a more streamlined approach such as the one adopted in the Common Data Environment (CDE) paradigm, is a better fit for this work. A CDE provides a centralized platform for effective data management, collaboration, and integration, serving as a single source of truth, and ensures consistency and reliability of data across the data ecosystem. Moreover, one of the goals of the GBN-DT platform is to leverage the transformative potential of Linked Data and its applications, in order to build robust and intelligent digital building twins that transcend the boundaries of traditional data integration approaches; this is also better coupled within the CDE paradigm. Particular attention will be paid to ISO 19650 processes using IFC (ISO 16739) and complementary file types.

We start this chapter by providing some background on Linked Data technologies and applications in the building sector, before presenting the Dynamic District Information Management (DDIM) server, the component that will enable the support for Linked Data in PROBONO. Then, we present the overall GNB common data space architecture, with the DDIM at its heart and the IMC connectors responsible for ingesting data from the various building physical twin sources.

4.1 Linked Data for Digital Building Twins

4.1.1 Background

As digital twins evolve into complex ecosystems that replicate the physical world with precision, the incorporation of Linked Data principles provides a powerful framework for seamlessly connecting and contextualizing diverse data sources into usable knowledge graphs. The principles of Linked Data are commonly referred to as the "5-star" model [3], which provides a gradual progression towards achieving fully interconnected and interoperable data:

1. **Use URIs (Uniform Resource Identifiers) as names for things:** URIs are used to uniquely identify resources, such as people, places, or concepts. Each resource should have a unique URI, which acts as a globally accessible identifier.
2. **Make URIs dereferenceable:** Dereferencing a URI means that when someone accesses the URI, they receive information about the resource it represents. By making URIs dereferenceable, Linked Data enables direct access to the data associated with a resource.
3. **Use RDF (Resource Description Framework) to provide useful information:** RDF is a standard for representing data and knowledge on the web. It allows the creation of statements in the form of subject-predicate-object triples, where the subject and object are identified by URIs. RDF provides a flexible way to describe relationships and attributes of resources.
4. **Include links to other URIs:** The true power of Linked Data lies in its ability to establish links between different resources. By including links to other URIs, data publishers can create connections between related resources, enabling navigation and exploration across datasets.
5. **Use RDF links to create a web of data:** Going beyond simple links, this principle encourages the establishment of rich interconnections by using RDF-based ontologies and vocabularies. By aligning data using shared vocabularies, the web of data becomes more cohesive and enables sophisticated data integration and reasoning.

In PROBONO, by leveraging the inherent flexibility and rich semantics of Linked Data, digital twin modelers can create digital replicas that not only capture the structure and attributes of assets but also establish meaningful relationships between entities, unlocking new possibilities for data discovery, inference, and collaboration.

4.1.2 Ontologies

Ontologies are formal representations of knowledge that define the concepts, relationships, and properties within a specific domain. They provide a structured and standardized way to describe entities and their interconnections. Ontologies are typically represented using formal languages like RDF, OWL (Web Ontology Language), or RDFS (RDF Schema) [4]. Ontologies play a crucial role in Linked Data by providing a shared vocabulary and a common understanding of concepts

within a domain. They facilitate interoperability and data integration across heterogeneous datasets.

In D3.16 “*Knowledge Graphs and Agent-Based Modelling*”, under the work conducted in WP3, there has been an introduction of some relevant ontologies for PROBONO (PROBONO D3.16). From this starting point, we investigated and present here the most frequently used ontologies in the building and the energy sectors.

4.1.2.1 Ontologies in the Building Sector

Ontology-based interoperability is an alternative to move from a model-centric towards a more decentralised semantic approach. For instance, using ontologies can facilitate integrating building energy data from multiple sources, even from standards such as IFC. This way, ontologies serve as a bridge to transfer data from one domain to another. This should facilitate the sharing of data from different software applications under a common representation, known and accessible to all and easily understood through the semantic relations defined in the scheme relation.

Different ontologies have been proposed for the construction industry in the last two decades. More specifically, in the construction domain, there are major ontologies used. To begin, **BIM (Building Information Modelling)** is a collaborative digital approach to the design, construction, and operation of buildings and infrastructure. It involves creating a 3D model of a building or structure that includes information about its physical and functional characteristics, such as geometry, materials, and performance data. BIM allows architects, engineers, contractors, and other stakeholders to collaborate on a single, coordinated model of a project, which can improve communication, reduce errors, and increase efficiency throughout the building lifecycle.

In the context of BIM, ontologies can be used to provide a formal and standardized representation of the concepts and relationships between them within the AEC (architecture, engineering, and construction) industry. This can include things like standardized definitions of building components, classifications of materials, and relationships between different types of building systems. By using ontologies in BIM, stakeholders can more easily share and interpret information within a project, leading to improved collaboration and better decision-making.

Over the past twenty years, there has been an increase in the number of proposed ontologies for the construction industry, which can be attributed, in part, to the growing use of semantic web technologies. Additionally, the W3C LBD CG, a community group focused on Linked Building

Data, has been active in proposing ontologies that follow a methodology based on use cases and requirements for linked data applications throughout the life cycle of buildings. Most ontologies are designed to structure information from a specific domain within the industry. Some of these have been generated from existing standards, with semantic meaning incorporated into the concepts of their schemes. There are two main categories of ontologies: those that aim to cover a broad domain, such as **ifcOWL** for BIM data, and those that include only core concepts that can be easily extended to specific domain ontologies, such as BOT. Simple ontologies are also advantageous because they are easier to maintain than complex ones. Even though **IFC is not strictly an ontology**, it can be considered a part of the broader semantic technology landscape. IFC in essence is a data model standard developed by the **buildingSMART** organization to describe the information and data exchange requirements for the architecture, engineering, construction, and facility management industries. IFC defines a standardized format for representing and exchanging building-related data and information, such as the geometry, spatial relationships, properties, and behaviours of building elements. IFC is intended to support interoperability among different software tools used in the construction industry and enable better collaboration among stakeholders throughout the project lifecycle.

IFCowl (Industry Foundation Classes Ontology) is an ontology developed to represent the Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) data model using Semantic Web technologies. It is designed to provide a machine-readable representation of the IFC data model, allowing it to be easily integrated with other ontologies and linked data sources. IFCowl defines classes, properties, and relationships between entities in the IFC data model, using OWL to create a formal, machine-readable description of the IFC schema. This allows the IFC data model to be easily queried and analyzed using Semantic Web tools and techniques. By representing the IFC data model as an ontology, IFCowl enables IFC data to be integrated with other Semantic Web data sources, providing a more comprehensive and interoperable representation of building and construction data. This can help improve the efficiency and accuracy of building and construction processes and enable new applications and services to be developed.

Building Ontology Topology (BOT) is an ontology that provides a formal specification of concepts and relationships used to represent the topology (i.e., the spatial relationships between parts) of building components and systems. It is designed to support the exchange and integration of data across different domains and applications in the AEC industry. The BOT ontology includes concepts such as spaces, elements, and relationships, and defines relationships between these concepts hierarchically. For example, a building may contain

several spaces, each of which may contain one or more elements (such as walls, floors, and ceilings). The BOT ontology defines relationships between these spaces and elements, such as containment, adjacency, and intersection. The BOT ontology is based on existing ontologies and vocabularies, including the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model, the ISO 15926 data model, and the IFC schema. It also includes additional concepts and relationships specific to building topology, such as relationships between openings (such as windows and doors) and the elements they penetrate. By using the BOT ontology, stakeholders in the AEC industry can more easily share and integrate data related to building topology across different software systems and platforms, leading to more efficient and effective collaboration and decision-making throughout the building lifecycle.

At larger geographical scales, the City Anatomy Ontology (CAO) which is an ISO standard (ISO 37105) and the CityGML ontology hold significant potential for capturing a diverse range of data and the relationships between those data, thus supporting multi-domain and multi-stakeholder analysis functionality.

4.1.2.2 Ontologies in the Energy Domain

Despite the existence of standards for interoperability, it is necessary to emphasise that it seems difficult to achieve full interoperability between BIM and energy simulation tools. An alternative to making a building's energy data more interoperable can be through the use of ontologies from the domain of energy modelling.

A widely used ontology in the energy domain is the Domain Analysis-Based Global Energy Ontology (**DABGEO**). The DABGEO ontology aims to improve interoperability between ontology-based energy management applications in large-scale energy management scenarios. It addresses the issue of heterogeneity in energy ontologies by providing common vocabularies for representing energy subdomains. The ontology is designed with a layered structure that balances reusability and usability, making it easier to reuse in different applications while also being practical and user-friendly. This approach helps to reduce the effort required for adoption and promotes the wider use of the ontology across different energy management scenarios.

The Smart Appliances REference (**SAREF**) ontology is a standard ontology for IoT and smart appliances domain that is also related to energy and buildings. It is an initiative of the European Commission to develop a common language for describing smart appliances and their functions and to facilitate their interoperability and integration into smart homes and buildings. SAREF provides a formal and standardized representation of smart appliances and their features,

capabilities, and functions. It includes a set of classes, properties, and relationships that enable the description of smart appliances in a machine-readable format. The ontology covers various aspects of smart appliances, such as their energy consumption, modes of operation, and user interfaces. One of the key advantages of SAREF is its ability to support interoperability between different appliances and their associated systems. By providing a common language for describing them, SAREF enables devices from different manufacturers and suppliers to communicate with each other and other smart systems in the home or building. It is also designed to be extensible, allowing for integrating new classes and properties to support emerging smart appliance technologies and use cases. This makes it a flexible and future-proof standard for the IoT and smart appliances domain.

There are many derivatives of **SAREF** ontology. Each of these ontology extensions builds on the foundational classes and properties of the SAREF Core but adds specific classes and properties that are relevant to a particular domain, allowing for greater specificity and flexibility in describing smart appliances and their associated systems in different contexts.

- **SAREF4ENER**⁵³: The SAREF4ENER ontology is an extension of the SAREF Core ontology that is specifically designed for the energy domain. It includes additional classes and properties for describing energy-related features of smart appliances, such as their energy efficiency, renewable energy sources, and energy consumption patterns.
- **SAREF4BLDG**: An extension of the core SAREF ontology designed to describe smart building applications, such as lighting, HVAC, security systems, and energy management.
- **SAREF4HEALTH**⁵⁴: The SAREF4HEALTH ontology is an extension of the SAREF Core ontology designed for the healthcare domain. It includes classes and properties describing health-related sensors, such as blood pressure and heart rate monitors, and their associated measurements and data.
- **SAREF4AGRI**⁵⁵: The SAREF4AGRI ontology is an extension of the SAREF Core ontology that is designed for the agriculture domain. It includes classes and properties for describing agricultural sensors, such as soil moisture and temperature sensors, and their associated measurements and data.
- **SAREF4CITY**⁵⁶: An extension of the core SAREF ontology, designed to describe smart city applications, such as traffic management, waste management, and environmental monitoring.
- **SAREF4WATR**, a water domain extension and **SAREF4LIFT**, a smart lift domain extension

Finally, **DNAs** ontology provides a well-defined framework for representing occupants' behaviour related to a building's energy efficiency. DNAs ontology comprises four key concepts. The first concept is occupants' *drivers*, which refers to indoor environmental factors that affect occupants' physical or psychological well-being. The second concept is occupants' *needs*, which encompasses the psychological or physical requirements of occupants. The third concept is occupants' *actions*, which relate to interactions between occupants and systems or activities undertaken to change environmental comfort conditions. The final concept is *systems*, which includes equipment or mechanisms that occupants can use to alter the environmental comfort conditions.

4.2 The Dynamic District Infrastructure Management Server

As previously mentioned, Linked Data provide a mechanism to interlink disparate data sources and interrogate them using semantic queries. The use of the Linked Data approach enables planners to comprehend resource requirements for infrastructure modifications by facilitating access to comprehensive information sources, spanning from individual building components to national scale.

The DDIM server showcases how linked data methods enable queries over vast and varied data sources, allowing for complex inquiries at different levels. The following section highlights the advantages of applying the DDIM server to Multi-scale Energy Modelling, its features, components, and a simple use case. The Server is a Django/Neo4J/NeoSemantics based server that provides connectivity for front-end software to create homogeneous knowledge graphs from heterogenous data sources such as CSV files, existing graphs and other data sources. The dataset that results can be investigated using semantic queries, as defined in SPARQL.

The described use case creates a hierarchy (buildings supplied by distribution network supplied by transmission network) to provide context for other information sources allowing their integration into a wider data network.

4.2.1 Features and Methodology

The graph is created using the following steps (note the steps described here are implemented through a user-friendly form-based interface):

1: Upload CSV Files – files are uploaded to the server. These are parsed and column headers are parsed and recorded. This serves three purposes

- It allows for knowledge discovery through the identification of data sources, as well as a description of the attributes that make these up. These meta-data are made available through the server as a data catalogue to allow user discover data contained by the server;
- It informs the definition of connection rules by allowing connections to be made between entities according to the ontology.
- Under the hood, Neo4J load/create/merge commands are issued to represent the data. Each CSV row represents a new entity in the graph.

2: Create Connection Rules – connection rules are used to define one of three relationships between entities created in step 1. These are

- Equivalent to – where two entities are considered to relate to the same real-world entity.
- Contains – where entity A is a child of entity B in a hierarchical relationship. Entity A can have many children.
- Contained-by – the inverse relationship of Contains (not created as Neo4J relationships are bi-directional).
- isa – used to relate data to classes – e.g., archetype data related to an entity.
- hasa – used to relate an entity to other data sources that provide further descriptions.

These relationships are created using the create/createrule/ RESTFUL API which accepts standard HTTP requests to GET and POST to the type. create/createrule/ is used to access individual rules. These relationships are described by the ontology shown in figure 6-A.

3: Rules are created by posting to the API. The POST call takes 5 parameters:

- relationship – one of 'equalto', 'contains', 'contained', 'isa' and 'hasa'
- filename1 and filename2 – filename of datasource uploaded earlier.
- joincolumn1 and joincolumn2 – the names of columns across which equivalence or other relationship is defined.

In the following section we demonstrate the use of DDIM in an application in the building sector.

4.2.2 DDIM application in the Building Sector

The decarbonisation of the heating and transport sectors are core parts of Irish Government climate policy, and it is envisaged that this will be achieved primarily through electrification of both. The Irish Government has set targets for six hundred thousand heat pumps to be installed by 2030, two thirds of which are to be installed in existing dwellings. This will also require significant retrofitting to raise the energy efficiency of these dwellings. Such large-scale electrification will have significant impacts on the electricity generation and transmission network. To understand the long-run power system impacts of this electrification, the ENGINE model was developed, which determines the least-cost development of the power system under future policy scenarios. Enhanced network effects and stochastic modelling in generation expansion planning: Insights from an insular power system.

The ENGINE model requires information on electricity demand at each of the 676 nodes in the transmission system, and so the impact of the electrification of heating at each node is required in order to determine the power system impacts of future electrification. The Irish Transmission System Operator EirGrid has developed projections of the electricity demand from heat pumps at national level only.

The DDIM, allowed the determination of demand in a “bottom-up” manner, incorporating household characteristics as well as the impact of retrofitting dwellings. Because the DDIM server’s functionality facilitated integration and querying of a greater number of data sources within the limitations of resources available to the project, a more extensive data set could be used for analysis.

The DDIM server has been tested in modelling the Irish Energy Network, first by 1-capturing the energy transmission nodes in the network, and then 2-associate small areas that represent distribution nodes (contained by one of the transmission nodes), each of the 3-buildings served by those distribution nodes, the DDIM server is also able to associate 4-other pieces information with that common context.

Figure 6. A) Underpinning ontology and B) example of a DDIM implementation architecture

The server provided data to an exploration tool that informs analysts that seek to explore the effects of large-scale adoption of electricity-intensive technologies (ie, heat pump) at the building level on local and national level electricity infrastructure.

The utility of the architecture was examined by establishing a data network to support Ireland's Economic and Social Research Institute (ESRI) analysts to investigate the impact of various decarbonisation scenarios on the Irish transmission and distribution networks. Large datasets were used to support this investigation, including details of 220 transmission nodes, c.16,500 small areas and approximately 2 million residential buildings.

A series of archetypes were developed, including as-is and energy consumption per residence archetype for numerous scenarios, including adopting heat pumps and electric vehicles. It was found that the DDIM approach admitted finer grained data analysis, improving the accuracy of the analysis. The analysis was supported development of a scenario exploration tool that was also described.

The DDIM Server is advantageous for the PROBONO project. Its flexibility will allow a broad range of homogenous data to be integrated into a heterogenous graph. The DDIM Server is being extended to cater for formats other than CSV, including IFC and Revit files. There will, for instance be associated with other building data to allow very expressive queries across hierarchical levels of data as well as across heterogenous data types and formats. The server will be further modified to allow it to be deployed via Docker containers and documentation updated, ensuring it will be easily deployed by project partners.

4.3 Common Data Space Architecture

In the architecture of the Green Building Neighborhood (GBN), we have adopted a Common Data Environment (CDE) approach to ensure effective data management, collaboration, and integration. The functionality of the CDE is sufficiently robust to accommodate data exchange across all phases of the building life cycle and facilitate compliance with all parts of the information exchange standard ISO 19650. To support this CDE approach, we will utilize the IMC connector coupled with a data lake, with the DDIM server also adding context to the stored data to facilitate seamless data exchange and enable interoperability among the various platform components.

In the following figure, the integrated GBN architecture is depicted:

Figure 7 Common Data Space architecture.

In the architecture, the IMC connectors play a crucial role in collecting and streaming data from the various LL sources, ensuring a continuous flow of real-time information. This data is then stored and organized in the data lake, creating a central repository of historical and streaming data. The data lake serves as a reliable and scalable storage solution, allowing efficient retrieval and analysis of vast amounts of data. The data lake is a fundamental component in the architecture, serving as a centralized storage repository for both streaming and static datasets

within the digital building twin ecosystem. It provides high-level functionalities such as data ingestion, storage, organization, and data discovery, which play a vital role in the successful implementation of digital building twins. Its design and implementation strategy is detailed in a separate section that follows.

Finally, to provide semantic context to the data, the DDIM server is employed, which enriches the information with metadata and exposes it as linked data. This semantic layer enhances the interoperability and understanding of the data, enabling seamless integration with other systems and applications.

The PROBONO Global Decision Support and Optimization platform leverages these three endpoints—the data streams from the connectors, historical data from the data lake and linked data from the DDIM server—to fuel its models and applications. The real-time data streams from the connectors enable monitoring and analysis of live operational data, facilitating real-time decision-making and control. The historical data stored in the data lake allows for deep insights, trend analysis, and retrospective analysis of past events. Additionally, the linked data provided by the DDIM server enables a semantic understanding of the data, enabling advanced querying, reasoning, and integration with external knowledge sources.

4.3.1 Data lake implementation

For the data lake implementation in PROBONO, traditional database systems like **MySQL**, **MongoDB**, and **PostgreSQL** will be considered. These systems offer different strengths and characteristics that cater to specific requirements within the project Living Labs. MySQL is a widely used relational database management system known for its stability, performance, and broad support. It offers strong scalability, durability, and robust security features, making it a suitable choice for digital building twins that require a mature ecosystem and extensive tooling. MongoDB, on the other hand, is a popular NoSQL document database that excels at handling unstructured or semi-structured data. Its flexible document model allows for easy data ingestion and adaptation to evolving data schemas, making it ideal for scenarios where the digital building twin ecosystem involves diverse data types and sources. PostgreSQL is a powerful open-source relational database management system known for its robustness, scalability, and extensibility. It offers ACID compliance, strong data consistency, and a wide range of data types and indexing options. PostgreSQL's rich feature set, including support for spatial data and advanced querying capabilities, makes it a suitable choice for digital building twins that require structured data management and complex relationships.

In addition to traditional database systems, cloud-based object storage services like **Amazon S3**, **Microsoft Azure Blob Storage**, and **Google Cloud Storage** are also viable options for the data lake component. These services provide highly scalable and durable storage solutions, making them suitable for managing large volumes of data within the digital building twin ecosystem. They offer robust security features, seamless integration with cloud platforms, and cost-effective storage options.

In the following table, we highlight the key characteristics of the above-mentioned implementation technologies:

Technology	Scalability	Durability	Security	Integration features
Amazon S3	Highly scalable	Highly durable	Robust security features	Seamless integration with AWS services
Microsoft Azure Blob Storage	Scalable	Durable	Comprehensive security	Seamless integration with Azure services
Google Cloud Storage	Scalable	Durable	Advanced security features	Seamless integration with Google Cloud services
PostgreSQL	Scalable	Highly durable	Robust security features	Advanced querying capabilities, support for structured data
MySQL	Scalable	Highly durable	Robust security features	Established relational database with broad support and tools
MongoDB	Scalable	Durable	Advanced security features	Flexible document model for handling unstructured data

Table 11: Data lake implementation technologies

As can be seen in Table 11, traditional database systems like MySQL, MongoDB, and PostgreSQL provide established and reliable solutions, each with their own strengths. On the other hand, cloud-based object storage services like Amazon S3, Microsoft Azure Blob Storage, and Google Cloud Storage offer highly scalable and durable options, coupled with advanced security features. Evaluating these factors allows for informed decision-making, tailoring the data lake architecture to the specific requirements of the PROBONO LLs.

It is likely that a mixture of technologies will be utilized in the PROBONO DTs, leveraging the strengths and capabilities in each case, towards the tailoring of the solution to the specific needs. As such, the data lake can achieve a balanced and optimized architecture that meets the unique demands of the project LLs.

Additionally, GBN platform applications that require real-time data streams can extract once the necessary metadata from the DDIM endpoint (e.g., which sensors are located in a specific room) and then use this metadata to subscribe in the appropriate topics in the IMC message broker.

The GBN common data space architecture, as it was designed, offers several advantages for the digital building twin ecosystem. By centralizing data management and promoting interoperability, it fosters collaboration among stakeholders, eliminates data silos, and enhances data consistency and accuracy. The IMC connectors enables efficient data processing and storage, while the DDIM server supports data integration and enables advanced querying capabilities. Together, these components provide a solid foundation for realizing the vision of the GBN project, empowering stakeholders to access, analyse, and utilize data effectively to drive sustainable and intelligent decision-making processes.

4.3.2 Specific Data Requirements for the GBN Platform

The GBN platform empowers users to gain comprehensive visibility and understanding of the digital twin ecosystem. It enables the development and deployment of advanced models, simulations, and applications that leverage the combined power of real-time streaming data, historical data, and linked data. This integration of diverse data sources and semantic context drives innovation, optimization, and effective decision-making within the digital building twin environment.

Regarding the linking of the GBN platform with the common data space, a set of specific data-related requirements were gathered from partners participating in T5.3 “GBN-DT Global Decision Support and Optimization Platform”. The following table presents the requirements gathered at this point:

Task / Tool	Data Requirements	Description	Type	Format	Access
ST5.3.1 <i>Probono information modelling framework</i>					
MIC	Simulation models metadata as specified in the MIC	Defining simulation models for reuse and identification of their functional domain	static	xml	Queries
ProBIM: BIM model augmented with human-centred design intent and analyses	Design + Operational phase: BIM model	Structure and organisation of building: Building elements, their relationships, and their geometries	static	IFC	API or direct access to the IFC file
	Design phase of building: none Operational phase of building (within digital twin): [high priority] CO2 sensor readings, room temperature readings, motion sensor data, status of automated facilities under management (e.g. state of windows, HVAC, etc.) [nice-to-have] light level sensor readings, sound measurements	Inferring occupancy (approximate) Used to reason about air quality (primary effects) and occupant experience and well-being with respect to thermal, acoustic, visual aspects	dynamic	JSON or streaming data as plain txt or raw byte data	API or query would be fine
ST5.3.4 <i>Tools for ML-based prediction scenarios</i>					

Prediction/ Forecast of energy production	Real-time energy production	This data describes the energy production for a building	Dynamic	JSON	API
Energy production Model training	Historic data about energy production	This data describes the energy production for a building for a long period of time.	Static	JSON	Data Base Query
Energy studies	External temperature Relative humidity Wind speed and direction Solar Radiation Dew temperature Precipitation Sea Level Pressure Occupancy	This data is essential to identify energy consumption profiles and develop prediction models	Dynamic	JSON/xml/netCDF	API
ST5.3.5 <i>Tools for air quality and energy management</i>					
Comfort virtual sensor	Real-time data from physical sensors installed in the building	Data which defines the building operating conditions is used to feed the Comfort virtual sensor	Dynamic	JSON	API
Ventilation assessment tool	Data provided by the final user: STL geometry and txt/json files	The data is used to set the details (geometry, boundary conditions...) of the CFD simulation to be done.	Static	Txt/JSON STL (geometry)	API
ST5.3.6 <i>GBN-GT Human Machine Interface</i>					
	1) Data Sources 2) Data mapping (what does the data represent, does it need to be further	All data and metadata collected in the PROBONO DTs that needs to be visualized	Real-time metrics or static data	Excel, csv, JSON, xml	Depending on where the use cases are storing

	processed and what is the expected output/visualisations)				their data and how it is exposed (query/APIs etc)
3)	User Stories/Storyboards				

Table 12: Data requirements from the GBN Platform

As the GBN platform further matures, the above requirements will go into deeper level of detail, guiding the implementation of the GBN common data space accordingly.

4.4 Security and Privacy Considerations

Data security and privacy are paramount considerations in the design and implementation of any digital system handling data from diverse sources; in order to ensure the protection and confidentiality of data within the PROBONO DTs the following security measures will be enforced in the GBN common data space:

- Secure Communications:** The IMC connectors will prioritize secure communication protocols, such as Transport Layer Security (TLS), to establish an encrypted channel for data transmission. TLS ensures that data remains confidential and protected against eavesdropping or unauthorized interception during transit. In addition, end-to-end encryption will be enforced so that data remains confidential and protected throughout its entire journey, guaranteeing that only the intended recipients can decrypt and access the data; this provides an additional layer of protection against unauthorized access or tampering during transit.
- Authentication and Authorization:** Robust authentication mechanisms are going to be implemented to verify the identity of users and components connected via the IMC connectors. This involves verifying credentials, such as usernames and passwords, or utilizing token-based authentication methods. Additionally, access control mechanisms, such as role-based access control (RBAC), will be considered to ensure that each user or component has appropriate permissions and access rights within the system.
- Data Encryption:** The data lake will employ data encryption techniques to protect sensitive information stored within its infrastructure. This will involve encrypting data at rest, which means encrypting the data when it is stored in storage systems or databases, as well as adding E2E encryption in its RESTful APIs. Similar methods will be

enforced also in the DDIM endpoints, ensuring as such that even if an unauthorized entity gains access to the stored data, they will not be able to decipher its content without the proper decryption keys.

By implementing the above measures in the GBN common data space, we aim to establish a secure environment for data access and transmission within the digital twin ecosystem, providing multiple layers of protection against potential data breaches and privacy violations.

5 The GBN Knowledge Base

The GBN Open Knowledge Base (OKB) will serve as an innovations observatory for enhanced visibility on the performance of GBN solutions that will be implemented in terms of the PROBONO project as well as from results of relevant projects to date. It will also include information about best practises and solutions, applicable legal frameworks, privacy, licensing, data governance mechanisms in place, standards, and technological challenges.

The Open Knowledge base is generally intended to be open to the public, as the purpose is to share knowledge and information with as wide an audience as possible. However, there may be certain pieces of information that need to be restricted, such as sensitive or confidential data.

5.1 Methodology and Development Technology

The GBN OKB will be developed in accordance to the user interface design principles with a focus on delivering the ultimate user experience and meeting the needs of the different types of users. The interface of the OKB will utilize the latest technology to ensure compatibility with multiple devices and be easily accessible from smartphones, tablets, desktop PCs and laptops. Additionally, the design and implementation processes will be centered around the user in order to ensure a simplified, user-friendly and efficient tool.

More specifically, the OKB interface design and implementation will be guided by the following the key Graphical User Interface (GUI) Design Principles [5]:

- **Clarity:** the interface should be visually, conceptually and linguistically clear.
- **Comprehensibility:** the interface should be easily understood and the flow can be easily followed.
- **Consistency:** the interface should be consistent throughout, meaning users should be able to easily navigate the interface without having to re-learn or adapt to different elements.
- **Control:** the user should be able to control the interaction.
- **Efficiency:** the user's eye and hand movements should be minimized, the transition between various systems control should flow easily and freely while navigation paths should be as short as possible.

- **Simplicity:** a simple, clean and uncluttered interface can improve usability and help users focus on the main tasks.

In order to achieve cross browser and multi device compatibility, technologies of HTML5, CSS3, and JavaScript will be used. These technologies offer a state-of-the-art user interface with new elements, attributes and behaviours as listed below:

- **Semantics:** allow the user to describe more precisely what the content is.
- **Connectivity:** allow the user to communicate with the server in new and innovative ways.
- **Offline and storage:** allow webpages to store data on the client-side locally and operate offline more efficiently.
- **Multimedia:** use plug-ins that allow the manipulation of new multimedia content (videos and audios).
- **2D/3D graphics and effects:** allow a much more diverse range of presentation options.
- **Performance and integration:** provide greater speed optimization and better usage of computer hardware.
- **Device access:** allow the use of various input and output devices.
- **Styling:** allow authors to write more sophisticated themes.
- **Knowledge graph:** graph databases allow users to query the project information for semantic queries, based on relationships between concepts captured in the OKB.
- **Large Language Models:** WordPress plugins allow connectivity to other functionalities, such as more advanced (e.g., semantic) search tools or chatbot-like capabilities.

5.1.1 Basic Features

5.1.1.1 User Management

The user management feature within the OKB will be responsible for handling user accounts. This includes tasks such as creating, deleting, editing, activating, and resetting user passwords, displaying user information, locking or unlocking accounts, and granting or revoking access to specific information based on the user's permissions.

The portal will allow users to create accounts and login to the portal. Users will be able to adjust their profile preferences, and thus customize the content of the portal pages based on those preferences. Additionally, users will have the option to filter their search, based on a selection of preferred categories, sub-categories and keywords. Also, users can access their profile from different devices and have access to the same portal content.

Users will also be able to enter the portal anonymously as guests, navigate through the portal and have access to information without being logged in. Users can choose preferred categories, sub-categories and keywords; however, these users will not have access to confidential information such as some project results, LL detailed development plans and solutions, paid standards etc.

The available roles in the OKB can be viewed in the list below:

- **System administrator:** The administrator of the OKB, which is eBOS since they are leading the development. This role is responsible for managing and maintaining the OKB and will have full access and control over the portal's functionalities, including user management, content management, set user roles and permissions and ensure smooth operation of the knowledge base. Also, the system administrator will oversee the overall security and privacy of the OKB.
- **Registered user:** This role will be created by the system administrator and assigned to PROBONO partners and LL leaders. These users will have access to a wide range of features and resources based on their role in the project. PROBONO partners and LL leaders will be able to contribute with new content, update existing information and participate in collaborative discussions related to the knowledge base. In addition, they will have access to confidential information such as project results, detailed LL development plans and standards purchased for use in the PROBONO project.
- **Anonymous user:** anonymous users are visitors who will be able to enter the OKB without creating an account. They will be able to navigate through the knowledge base and access publicly available information, best practices and general resources without personalized features. Anonymous users will have the ability to filter their search based on preferred categories, sub-categories and keywords, however, they will not have access to confidential information such as specific project results, detailed LL development plans and implemented solutions or paid standards.

5.1.1.2 Search Tool

The search tool will be a main feature of the OKB that will give the opportunity to the user to find relevant information quickly and effectively. It is important to note that the knowledge gained from WP1-4 and the LLS along with the knowledge graphs that will be developed, will be stored in the DDIM server which will be linked with the OKB. The user will be able to use keywords and use the advanced search options to refine and narrow down the results, which will be delivered to the user in a simple format and a user-friendly design. We will also explore the feasibility to use large language models to generate indexes (embeddings) that will ultimately facilitate semantic search. This could ultimately lead to a ChatGPT-like approach enabling the user to query the knowledge based in natural language and get factual answers, providing links to reference content.

5.1.1.3 User-generated content

The OKB will enable users to contribute their own information by allowing them to upload content. This feature will only be available to registered users, who will be able to upload new data files, documents or media files within the knowledge base or update existing information, expanding its content and making it more comprehensive. To ensure the reliability and integrity of the knowledge base, the content moderation will be performed by the system administrator. Therefore, the submitted content will go through a quick review process in order to verify the information, check for errors and maintain the overall quality of the database.

5.1.1.4 Cross-Browser and Multi Device Compatibility

The OKB will function consistently across major browsers such as Google Chrome, Firefox, Safari and Internet Explorer by utilizing the latest technology for design and implementation as mentioned above. All users will be able to access the same content through a single URL, while the site's appearance will adjust dynamically based on the type of the device used, resolution and orientation.

5.1.2 Architecture and Development Technology

In order to decide how to develop the OKB, several options were considered such as Custom-Built Website, Content Management Systems (CMS) and e-commerce platforms. Developing a website from scratch might offer flexibility and control, however, it can be time consuming and costly, therefore the option to develop a custom-built website was rejected. Comparing the other solutions and taking into consideration the desired features as described earlier, it was

decided to develop the OKB utilizing WordPress since it satisfies the main requirements and functions desired. WordPress is the most popular, free, open-source CMS, that is also user-friendly and highly customizable. Specifically, WordPress has the following benefits compared to other solutions:

- **Ease of Use:** WordPress is known for its user-friendly interface and intuitive CMS since it allows non-technical users to easily create, edit and manage content without any coding knowledge required.
- **Customizability:** WordPress offers a wide range of themes and plugins that can be utilized to fit specific needs. The themes available have a clean and organized layout making it easy for users to navigate and find information. Also, the variety of plugins available, allow the addition of functionalities such as advanced search, user feedback and upload function that are essential for the OKB.
- **Scalability:** WordPress is highly scalable and can accommodate both small and large knowledge bases allowing the user to start with a basic setup and gradually expand as the requirements grow. Also, it can support a large volume of content without significant performance issues, that is ideal for the OKB where there will be huge amounts of data and information to be included.
- **Cost-Effectiveness:** WordPress is an open-source platform and while it may offer paid themes, plugins etc, the overall cost of building and maintaining a WordPress-based OKB is generally lower compared to other solutions.

The technical architecture of the OKB will be based on the technical architecture of WordPress. The figure below provides the technical architecture and main components of the OKB, how the components communicate and how data flows between the various components.

Figure 8: PROBONO OKB Technical Architecture

The main areas of this architecture include the request-response cycle between the browser and WordPress, WordPress and the query/results between WordPress and the MySQL Database [6]. When the user makes a request through his browser, the web server sends a response with the

HTML content of the home page along with other files that could be CSS, JavaScript or image files that are needed to load the web page according to the template selected. It should be noted that templates in WordPress consist of template files that are PHP files, style sheet files, JavaScript files, Image files and some other ones like functions.php [7].

5.2 Front-end Initial Designs

The initial designs of the GBN Knowledge Base include mock-ups that demonstrate its user interface and features. The mock-ups show a user-friendly interface that provides easy navigation to various sections of the knowledge base, including data sources, LLs, best practices, and solutions. The designs also show the various categories and subcategories that the data will be classified under, allowing users to quickly and easily access the information they need. The initial designs demonstrate that the GBN Knowledge Base will be an intuitive and user-friendly resource for anyone looking to implement GBN solutions.

5.2.1 Site Structure

Creating a good site structure is important for achieving optimal user-experience by simplifying navigation, providing better results and increasing the overall site quality. In order to achieve this, it is important to include elements to enhance the architecture such as navigation menus, categories and subcategories, header and footer [7]. The basic structure of the knowledge base will be hierarchical and in particular top-down. This means that the homepage is on top, then below are the top-level pages and then the sub-pages. To achieve such a structure, the content will be divided in categories. Figure 9 shows an initial categorization that will be further developed and enhanced when the final content of the KB will be defined.

Figure 9. PROBONO OKB Site Categorization Structure

5.2.2 Home page

The front page of the OKB is the “Home Page” (Figure 10), where users can see the main categories of information (side bar), the search tool and the most popular search results. The

Figure 10. PROBONO OKB - Home Page

users can also find the project's description under "About" or links to the project's social media pages as well as sign in/register to gain access to more results and confidential information.

5.2.3 Search results

Using the search function, the user can search within the entire knowledge base and the results are shown in a grid view with a title, an image and a short description as presented on Figure 11.

The screenshot displays the 'GBN Open Knowledge Base' search results interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home', 'About', and 'Sign In/Register' options. A search bar is located below the navigation bar. The main content area is titled 'Search Results' and contains a grid of six search results. Each result includes a title, a representative image, and a short description. The results are: 'Green Building (GB)', 'Green Neighbourhoods', 'Green Buildings And Neighbourhoods (GBN)', 'DGNB Certification', and two 'Search Result ...' entries. A sidebar on the left provides navigation options such as 'State Of The Art', 'GBN Solutions', 'Legal Framework', 'Living Labs Description', 'Definitions', and 'Other Category'. The bottom right corner features social media icons and a 'Follow Us On' prompt.

Figure 11 PROBONO OKB - Search Results

The user can refine the search results by selecting specific filters either by keywords or specific categories as shown in the following figure:

Figure 12: PROBONO OKB - Search Results Filtering

5.2.4 Sign In/Register

As mentioned above, the portal will allow users to register and login, providing access to confidential information. The login screen can be seen on Figure 13.

Figure 13: PROBONO OKB - Login Screen

5.3 Next steps

The next steps for developing the OKB include several key activities. First, the gathering of end-users' feedback will be initiated by engaging with the Living Labs. This will involve presenting the prototype of the OKB to obtain their input and understanding their additional needs and requirements. Additionally, the prototype of the OKB will be shared with other project partners to gather additional feedback as well as to request for data and information that will be incorporated to the OKB to enrich its content. Moreover, data collection, which has already commenced, will continue for most of the project duration. This ongoing data collection is crucial as it forms the foundation of the information that will be available through the knowledge base. As the data collection is progressed, the structure of the OKB will be further defined and the process of categorizing the data will ensure an organized and accessible knowledge base.

6 Conclusion

The design phase of the T5.2 components is a crucial step in establishing a robust and efficient data ingestion and management infrastructure for the GBN platform. This document summarizes the outcomes from this process. After investigating available solutions and relevant state of the art, it was deemed that a CDE approach was best suited for the needs of the GBN common data space, to lay the foundation for effective data integration, collaboration, and decision-making within the digital building twin ecosystem.

The PROBONO data connectors, which will be used in the Digital Twin, architecture and constituent components were defined, as well as the most prominent implementation solutions for each of them. The architecture was designed with the aim of providing stakeholders with a centralized platform for collecting, processing, and managing data, ensuring data consistency, accessibility, and accuracy throughout the GBN-platform users. Additionally, the leveraging of a linked data server, the DDIM, in the GBN common data space is presented in this report, which enhances the interoperability and promotes a standardized data representation. This server leverages Linked Data and Semantic Web technologies, enabling data integration and advanced querying capabilities.

Finally, the progress made in shaping the Open Knowledge Base (OKB), that will complement the GBN platform, is also included in this document. The OKB design will prioritize user experience, adhering to GUI design principles such as clarity, comprehensibility, consistency, control, efficiency, and simplicity. Technologies like HTML5, CSS3, JavaScript, and large language models will ensure compatibility across browsers and devices, while user management features, a robust search tool, and user-generated content capabilities will enhance the OKB's functionality. The technical architecture will be based on WordPress, offering ease of use, customizability, scalability, and cost-effectiveness. Gathering feedback from end-users and incorporating data will be the focus of the next steps, ensuring the OKB meets the needs and requirements of stakeholders and becomes a valuable resource for implementing GBN solutions.

All of the above lay a solid foundation for the subsequent stages of the T5.2; the designs and implementation technologies identified during this phase are the first step towards a robust and scalable solution for interconnecting DT subsystems and creating a cohesive data ecosystem for the GBN concept. Moving forward, the implementation and deployment phases will bring these designs to life, applied and tested in the project LLs.

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